

The impact of emotional profile on learning: the case of public elementary school learner

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Abstract:

The learner experiences many emotions: getting ready at home, on the way to school, in front of the portal, in the playground and in the classroom. These emotions need to be diagnosed, assessed and taken into consideration for the purpose of creating an atmosphere conducive to learning. Teachers need to be aware of their learners' emotional state in order to be in tune with them (knowing how to deal with emotionally sensitive cases, devising appropriate teaching strategies, etc.) The present work highlights the emotional state of the child during the three primary cycles following an analysis of certain cases in Moroccan public schools.

We are going to look at these emotions from the point of view of the teacher and the protagonist (the learner), with the aim of developing coaching approaches that teachers can adopt to help their students intelligently manage their emotions, strengthen their emotional identity and consequently enhance their learning

Keywords: emotion, learner, coaching, emotion management, emotional skills

1. Introduction:

At school, the psychological side of the learner is of increasing interest to teachers. Given the high rates of divorce, family problems, family disintegration... not to mention the consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic and quarantine on the psychological and emotional feelings of the entire population. As a teaching community, we cannot expect audiences to be receptive, balanced and responsive to school regulations anymore.

There's no longer a question of teaching while neglecting learners' feelings, given that their emotions, a catalyst in the teaching-learning operation, imminently influence their lives at school.

The emotions experienced by every learner at school (joy, surprise, anger, excitement, panic....) have a positive or negative impact on learning. Imbued with a panoply of emotions on the way to school, in front of the gate, in the playground, in the classroom, with his or her classmates, in front of the teacher and other members of the educational setting. The child expects his or her emotional state to be the focal point during learning. Unfortunately, however, due to lack of time, staff, training or resources, some teachers intentionally or unintentionally neglect these emotions in order to teach with as little effort as possible.

Emotions, one of the key concepts of coaching, can be managed. As "*an approach to support [...] aimed at achieving the highest level of success [...] and fulfillment*" (Robert, 2011, p. 455). This accompaniment is multidimensional; it adopts a holistic approach that encompasses the mental and emotional to optimize performance (Pierre Angel & Patrick Amar, 2015). Pedagogical coaching of various kinds can provide invaluable assistance to teachers, with the aim of "equipping" them with pedagogical approaches needed to manage emotions.

In the light of these facts, **how can coaching, and more specifically instructional coaching, compensate for the lack of emotional management in learners?**

Several questions emerge:

- What emotions do children feel most at school?
- How do teachers deal with the negative emotions of their students?
- What teaching approaches could be used to mitigate the effects of these emotions?
- How can we help students to better manage their emotions so that they don't get in the way of their learning?

Our topic, " The impact of emotional profile on learning: the case of public elementary school learner ", draws its importance in scientific research in general and in education in particular from the influence of emotions on students' motivation and interest in learning. Its importance

also stems from the crucial relationship between the emotional climate of the classroom, learners' concentration and their emotional, mental and cognitive development.

It aims to provide primary school teachers with a number of coaching approaches for regulating the emotions that can impede learners' learning and, consequently, foster their satisfaction with school.

The research is structured as follows: The conceptual framework explores the concept of emotions and the place they occupy at school, based on studies carried out by several researchers. The empirical framework sets out the context, objectives and research questions, as well as the tools adopted. The methodology section describes the qualitative survey carried out; this involved two focus groups with learners to diagnose the emotions most felt in class. A semi-directive interview with teachers to explore their views on the emotions experienced and demystify the methods used in class to help learners master them. The results enabled us to draw up an emotional profile of learners in the three primary cycles, highlighting the importance of emotions in learning and how they are handled in the classroom. The discussion interprets coaching approaches for efficient emotion management, with a view to enhancing life at school. The conclusion summarizes a number of recommendations for valuing emotions in teaching practice.

First, let's take a brief look at the definition of emotion, its characteristics and types, before turning to the place of emotions in the classroom.

2. Emotions, a few definitions:

Certainly, we are affected by our emotions. We can switch from one emotion to another, or feel several emotions at ones, depending on the situation. It is a reaction, even a riposte, to everything that surrounds us. Even if we appear calm, emotions have an imperative influence on us.

It is “*constellation of high-intensity responses involving typical expressive, physiological and subjective manifestations*” (Tamisier, 1999, p. 322).

Emotion is therefore a response triggered by an emotional situation (Doron & Parot, 2007, p. 250). This vivid response shows our involvement and subjectivity through its expression on our physiognomy and/or our bodily state.

The emotion can be painful or pleasant. It is so intense and brief (Sillamy, 2010, p. 103) that the organism quickly returns to its normal state. This character distinguishes it from feeling, since “*emotion is the immediate reaction, very often fleeting, whereas usually follows emotion. It is in the background, much longer-lasting*” (Gueguen, 2018, p. 41)

There are six basic emotions: joy, sadness, anger, fear, surprise and disgust (Doron & Parot, 2007, p. 250). These and other compound emotions such as excitement, anxiety, panic... or even combined ones (to experience two emotions at the same time, which can sometimes be contradictory) like joy and sadness, anger and disappointment... occur anywhere; at home, at work, on the street, ...as well as at school.

3. Emotions at school:

Like all human beings, children are invaded by emotions and especially at school; it is a world full of emotions! At an early age, they are invited to leave their comfort zone, or almost, for a totally different environment (a path to follow, classmates to rub shoulders with, educational staff to familiarize themselves with, homework to do...) where they have to learn, integrate and live on an equal footing with their family environment.

However, considered a troublesome accessory and a sign of weakness (Gueguen, 2018, p. 34) *“the emotional dimension of learning at school has been largely neglected, and it is only in the theories dealing with motivation that it is mentioned”* (Lafortune et al., 2004, p. 5).

Around the 1930s, educational researchers paid attention to anxiety as the first emotion studied in learners (Pekrun, 2014). Some psychologists pay tribute to the emotional life of the child, asserting that emotions should not be a source of instability, turbulence and anxiety (Malrieu, 1956, p. 86). Other studies testify to the primordial role of emotions in learner motivation (Gläser-Zikuda & Mayring, 2004). But lately, the psychology of emotions, learning and emotional intelligence is gaining momentum on this subject (Lafortune et al., 2004, p. 5). The emotional state is no longer sidelined. Through our field study, we were able to bring more visibility to this subject.

4. Empirical study:

4.1. Background:

Direct contact with students has enabled us to observe their psychological and emotional state through their behavior in class; joy, sudden fear, panic... the causes seem clear to us (activity outside class, exercise or assignment not completed...) but sometimes incomprehensible. That is the reason behind this slightly more in-depth study, to unravel these emotions, their influence and how to make them conducive to learning.

On the other hand, the neglect of emotions by teachers cannot be a premeditated act, so diagnosing this problem from the teachers' point of view seems very important in order to measure the degree of interest they take in emotional state of their learners, and by what means to deal with states that suffer from emotional failure.

4.2.Objectives

Acting on the emotional state of students guarantees their success at school; this is ultimate objective of this study. In order to achieve this, we need to accomplish another objective just as crucial as the first: to equip teachers with all the necessary means to act positively on the emotional state of learners, guaranteeing a pleasant atmosphere for learning. We will be looking at this in the next few lines.

4.3.Research questions:

Are teachers aware of the importance of emotions in learning? And if they are aware of the important role played by emotional state, how do they deal with the negative emotions experienced by their students? What approaches do they use to mitigate the effects of these emotions, so that they do not get in the way of their students' learning?

4.4.The sample:

To answer these questions, we chose two public-sector elementary schools, one in a rural area and the other in an urban area of Casablanca.

At the same time, we diagnosed and analyzed students' emotional state from the point of view of public primary school teachers, by interviewing them on this subject.

4.5.Search tools:

The focus group seems to be the best tool, suitable with learners and serving, precisely, our qualitative research. It's an open discussion in which interaction between participants is used as a means of data collection and as a focus for analysis (Kitzinger et al., 2004). By putting the children in a calm, jovial atmosphere conducive to gathering fruitful data about their emotions on the way to school, about how they feel when they are praised, encouraged or even provoked and criticized, about how they feel when faced with a difficulty in class and how they react. Exchanging ideas within a group and listening to their peers give their opinions encourage children to talk and express their feelings.

As for the semi-directive interview, a qualitative data collection technique (Imbert, 2010) largely meets our intentions; we aim to get the opinion of as many teachers as possible. It consists of several open-ended questions that will enable us to understand the learner's feelings, as well as the means used by teachers to manage emotions that disrupt learning, with the aim of designing a coaching approach capable of developing emotional competence in learners.

5. Study methodology:

5.1. For focus group:

The choice of two public elementary schools in Casablanca- One urban and one rural- gives us a comparative view of learners in the two sectors, and enables us to study both samples objectively, without leaning towards one particular sector. We carried out the focus group one month after the start of the new school year, to give students time to get used to the new environment (school, class, level, teachers, classmates; etc.).

We would like to mention from the outset that the 2 focuses are in dialectal Arabic to facilitate exchange. As a result, children feel at ease and respond fluently without being linguistically stressed.

The first focus (table 1) was carried out in a school in an urban area in the center of Casablanca. The sample was chosen by the teachers, who tried to vary it according to the level of learning (excellent, average and low):

Table 1: first focus sample

Cycle	boys	girls	total
First cycle (1 st and 2 nd grade of primary education)	3	3	6
Second cycle (3 rd and 4 th grade of primary education)	3	4	7
Third cycle (5 th and 6 th grade of primary education)	2	4	6
Total	8	11	19

Source: authors

The second focus group involved a school in a rural area near Casablanca. We proceeded in the same way as the first focus group: (table 2)

Table 2: second focus sample

Cycle	Boys	Girls	Total
First cycle (1 st and 2 nd grade of primary education)	3	3	6
Second cycle (3 rd and 4 th grade of primary education)	3	4	7
Third cycle (5 th and 6 th grade of primary education)	2	4	6
Total	8	11	19

Source: authors

All were invited to express themselves on a number of questions related to their feelings about school and the classroom, in an attempt to pinpoint their state and draw up their emotional profile.

5.2. For the semi-directive interview:

This interview is intended for Moroccan public elementary school teachers. Opting for a semi-structured interview is the best choice for our qualitative survey, in order to gather as much data as possible on the emotions most frequently expressed in the primary classroom, which can help us identify the learner’s profile according to their emotions in the classroom.

We carried out the survey using Google Forms software, and distributed it via a link on the WhatsApp application to fellow teachers working in state elementary school, who in turn shared it with their teacher friends, while fully preserving the anonymity of the participants. This way of disseminating the interview allows respondents to feel more at ease when faced with sensitive questions (Napoli, 2022), particularly those related to their classroom practice.

5.3. Presentation and interpretation of results:

-The following responses reached 40: eight male and thirty-two female teachers (figure 1). The

Figure 1: Gender distribution

source: Authors

male minority is due to the greater female representation in public primary education.

-The teachers are divided almost equally between urban and rural areas. This diversity gives a holistic idea of the learner in both areas. (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Distribution by work area

Source: Authors

-Five teachers work under contract, compared with thirty-five permanent teachers.
-Four teachers have less than five years' experience. Six others have between five- and ten-years' experience. 40%, or sixteen teachers, have between eleven- and twenty-years' experience. The remaining fourteen have been in the domain for over twenty years (figure 3). The variety of years of experience enriches the responses and enables us to get opinions of both young and experienced teachers.

Figure 3: Distribution by years of experience

Source: Authors

-Generally speaking, the participating teachers are distributed as follows: (table 3)

Table 3: Distribution of participating teachers

	First cycle		Second cycle		Third cycle	
	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men
Number	12	2	10	2	10	4
Total	14		12		14	

Source: authors

-In terms of assigned grade levels, fourteen teachers have a first cycle (six of whom have the first year and eight in the second year). Twelve teachers in the second cycle equally divided between the third and fourth year. Fourteen teachers in the third cycle, seven of whom teach the sixth year.

-According to the language taught (figure 4), seventeen teachers teach Arabic and eighteen teach French. Four teachers teach both Arabic and French. Only one teaches the Amazigh language.

Figure 2: Distribution by language taught

Source: Authors

-This diversity, in terms of gender, area of assignment, recruitment status, years of experience, level of education and language taught, is a capital asset for this qualitative questionnaire; it's fertile raw material that will add richness to the results obtained.

5.3.1. The emotional profile of the public elementary school learner:

For the sake of visibility, we have synthesized the data collected from focus groups with learners and interviews with teachers, and presented them in form of a summary table. This mode of grouping will enable us to summarize the emotional state of learners for each cycle, while comparing converging and diverging points in the opinions of the two actors.

- ***The emotional profile of the first cycle primary learner:*** (table 4)

It is the most difficult profile to pin down emotionally, because they are still young, uncertain and do not know exactly how they feel, and cannot express themselves credibly about their emotions. All the same, we have tried to extract as much information as possible.

Table 4: emotional profile of the first cycle learner

	According to the teacher	Depending on the learner
When congratulated:	Happy and proud	happy
If their answer is wrong:	Sad, disappointed, angry, ashamed, worried or may feel no emotion at all.	Sad, angry or unaffected.
If they are reprimanded:	Sad, ashamed, disappointed, angry, fearful, disturbed. they may seem indifferent.	Afraid or angry with themselves. Rare when they do not feel offended.
If encouraged:	Joy and pride with self-assurance and self-confidence.	They like to be encouraged; it pleases them and makes them happy.
Faced with difficulty:	they often ask for help. If they cannot, because of fear, shyness, communication difficulties or language problems.	Rarely frightened, they ask their teacher for help. they may be frightened if they cannot solve a problem.
The emotions most often expressed in class:	Joy, fear, panic, pride, anger, sadness and indifference.	They enjoy out-of-class activities and feel happy and motivated.
During recess:	Joy, excitement and sometimes sadness.	

Source: Authors

- ***The emotional profile of the second cycle primary learner:*** (table 5)

Children begin to realize their emotions and express them better than in the first cycle.

Table 5: Emotional profile of the second cycle learner

	According to the teacher	Depending on the learner
When congratulated:	Happy, proud and motivated	Joy and motivation.
If their answer is wrong:	They are sad frustrated, angry and unmotivated. Sometimes indifferent.	Sadness or anger, or sometimes indifference.
If they are reprimanded:	Sad, ashamed and angry, and hardly indifferent.	Afraid or angry with themselves. Sad if their teacher is angry with them. Rarely indifferent.
If encouraged:	They are happy and motivated.	It is very important to their motivation and happiness.
Face a difficulty:	They ask their teachers for help. Sometimes they cannot, because they are afraid, ashamed of being humiliated or sensitive about being misunderstood or judged.)	They are afraid of punishment if the lesson has already been explained, and at ease if it is a new one. They ask their teacher for help. Sometimes they are afraid and cannot ask for it.
The emotions most often expressed in class:	Joy, fear, panic, sadness, motivation and indifference	They feel happy motivated when their teacher suggests an out-of-class activity.
for the recess:	They are all happy.	

Source: Authors

▪ ***The emotional profile of the third cycle primary learner:***_(table 6)

they present a mature profile, more confident of their answers than a child of the first or second cycle, but richer in emotions too. The learner begins to understand their emotions, to accept them and to coax others by hiding them: they begin to manage their emotions intelligently and to have an emotional identity that characterizes them. This is an interesting profile, as the learner begin to analyze their teacher's personality and react accordingly. If the teacher is "cool", the learner is comforted and motivated to take an active role in learning, and can ask for help if necessary.

Table 6: emotional profile of the third cycle learner

	According to the teacher	Depending on the learner
When congratulated:	They are happy, proud, motivated and more self-confident.	They are proud and happy.
If their answer is wrong:	they feel sad discouraged, angry, disappointed, unmotivated and even ashamed.	Clam, sometimes disappointed, sad, angry, irritated and tense.
If they are reprimanded:	They are sad, ashamed, angry, disappointed and regret their mistakes.	They are disappointed, sad, tense, angry with themselves and afraid of being punished.
If encouraged:	they experience joy and motivation.	They are happy, excited and motivated.
Face a difficulty:	they usually ask their teachers for help. If they hesitate, it is for fear of being mocked or humiliated by their classmates.	Frightened if the problem has already been explained, and cannot bring themselves to tell their teacher. At ease with a new situation and do not hesitate to ask for help. They are able to hide their emotions for fear of their classmates' mocking and intimidating reaction and what they will think of them.
The emotions most often expressed in class:	Joy, panic, fear, sadness and disgust.	they enjoy out-of-class activities and feel more motivated when the whole class is involved.
For the recess:	Joy and excitement. Rarely fear and panic.	

Source: Authors

After tracing the emotional profile of learners in the two elementary school drawn by the teachers and by the learners themselves, there is a very high degree of similarity between the two points of view, with only minor differences as to the causes of certain emotions.

The common basic emotions felt along the cycles are joy, fear, panic and sadness. Other emotions such as pride, anger, excitement and disgust are manifested unevenly.

To remedy these emotions, especially the negative ones that get in the way of learning, teachers try a variety of ways to help their learners.

5.3.2. Teaching methods adopted with emotionally sensitive learners:

By “emotionally sensitive”, we mean a child’s immoderate emotional reaction to a classroom situation. They feel emotions more intensely than others and more strongly than average (Karyn D. Hall, 2014).

Based on our descriptive observation in the classroom, an emotionally sensitive learner is a child who gets hurt easily and cannot hide their dismay when they have to go to the blackboard. They react intensely when “teased” by their classmates, when faced with their helplessness in the face of an exercise or a problem he cannot solve... in short, towards their environment - the trigger for their emotional reaction.

When interviewed to ask this question, thirty-three teachers said they react differently to emotionally sensitive learners. They adopt different strategies with them, cited verbatim as follows:

- *“I talk to him gently, explaining that he has nothing to fear to motivate him,*
- *I try to understand them, to encourage them, not to evaluate them solely on their academic performance, but to see their favorite area and how they excel in it. Sometimes these students are gifted in other activities such as drawing, singing and writing, so I try to support them in this and it helps them to enjoy school and above all to feel confident about having a role to play,*
- *I treat them with more affection so as not to hurt their feelings*
- *Don’t embarrass the student in front of his friends,*
- *Be careful not to be hurt by harsh words,*
- *Flexibility and adaptation of learning levels,*
- *Kissing them, cuddling them,*
- *I encourage them,*
- *I behave differently with him, taking his condition into consideration, presenting activities appropriate to his level and abilities, and simplifying to the point of so that he can respond,*
- *Being closer and more attentive,*
- *Tell a story close to how he feels,*

- *Like a mother or a friend,*
- *Patience, love, encouraging him, looking for his strengths and asking his classmates to applaud him;*
- *Create a friendly relationship between teacher and learners,*
- *Be more attentive to them,*
- *I spend more time with them, listen to them and then react according to the situation,*
- *The calm,*
- *Speak in a low voice,*
- *I first listen to him to diagnose his case and then give him psychological support,*
- *Be understanding and give them the psychological support they need,*
- *Cuddles all the time, I lower my voice with them, I give them responsibilities in class, I always put my hand on their heads... candy, lollipop...,*
- *I always listen to him to understand him better, and this helps me to know which method will be best for him.”*

From the teachers' responses, we note that they take their learners' emotional state into consideration the best they can; being more attentive to them, speaking to them calmly, gently, cuddling and encouraging them, even spoiling them with sweets... but the emotional sensitivity or emotionality remains there, waiting for the next situation to trigger it another time.

Some try to heal the wound by being calm, attentive and understanding towards the situation, diagnosing the problem and psychologically supporting their students. However, these actions are carried out by only five of the forty teachers questioned. And we have no idea what kind of support is given, or how effective it is.

Teachers' lack of soft skills is the reason for their inability to provide effective help in this area. This failure influences their teaching practice and the pedagogical relationship with their learners. It is due to a lack of training in emotional management and the pedagogy with which to apply it with their students.

Instructional coaching can provide teachers with effective solutions to the problem of emotional management, since emotions are one of the key concepts in coaching. It can help teachers understand emotions, identify them, distinguish between them and help their learners manage them. This is the point we will focus on in the next paragraph.

6. Discussion:

Coaching approaches for better emotional management:

When we mention skills among other things, we talk about coaching as a means of “*providing help and support to develop internal skills*” (Higy-Lang & Gellman, 2000, p. 4). Recommended in the classroom, pedagogical coaching, as a means of intervention at the moment of difficulty with all stakeholders; teachers, learners and parents (Mouzoune, 2010). It can only achieve surprising improvements in this area. Using it directly with learners, or even with teachers, as a process based on the communication of feeling and self-awareness (Kurz et al., 2017), will enable the acquisition and mastery of these emotional skills by the latter, who will inculcate them in their pupils as an extracurricular activity, motor activity or even as an interval between lessons within the classroom.

We can hardly detach ourselves from our emotions, we are not machines. However, we can regulate those that tend to invade us with such power that they can block us or make us impulsive, or drive us to commit regrettable acts much later.

With emotional training (Sprung et al., 2015), helping learners to control their emotions is possible, essentially those that inhibit their learning in the classroom and can likely affect their academic, social, relational lives... leading them to failure. Moreover, this is by no means a recent idea, as it has long been argued that “*the child must become capable of rapidly overcoming emotional shock, and he must nevertheless remain sensitive to all changes in the situation*” (Malrieu, 1956, pp. 86 and 87).

And for them to be able to overcome these emotions, and acquire empathy and good social interactions (Gentaz, 2017), they need to acquire emotional skills (Mikolajczak, 2020, p. XIX) capable of helping them manage them:

- **Identifying emotions:** “*by identifying emotions, everything happens as if this reduces their intensity*”(Retuerta, 2016, p. 39). The child needs to be able to identify emotions and those of their peers. This requires learners to be able to identify and differentiate between basic emotions.
- **Understanding emotions:** the causes of the emotion, and its positive or negative effects, experienced by the learner or his/her peers. “*Children’s understanding of emotion is an important aspect of cognitive development*” (Sprung and al., 2015, p. 3). We therefore need to help learners through situations that help them understand emotions and their causes (Lafortune et al., 2004). In this case, emotion identification exercises (photos,

physiognomic drawings, riddles...) can help assimilate basic emotions for the first cycle, as well as compound or mixed emotions later with the second and third cycles.

- **Express your emotions:** expressing your emotions helps protect your physical, mental and psychological health. Expressing your emotions to your peers will help to build good emotional and social ties. Explanatory interviewing is the best way. Through targeted questioning to reflect on the emotional situation experienced and be able to describe it analogically, the learner can express themselves clearly with their teacher about the emotions they feel, identify their causes with the aim of modifying his emotional perceptions (Mouzoune, 2010, p. 92).

The use of stories (Rutledge, 2016) can also be a good way of pushing learners, implicitly, to become aware of their emotions, to acquire a certain language for expressing what they feel and the imperative of regulating or modifying them, as the hero of the story does. Choosing a story in which the learner can see themselves in the hero's profile, the teacher exploits the beliefs, life context, resources and resistances of the target student to identify with it, understand its morale and make efforts, imitating the good actions of the stories told, to transform negative emotions into positive ones, pleasant and motivating for learning.

- **Regulating emotions:** in order to “*retain their helpful features while limiting their destructive aspects*” (John & Gross, 2004, p. 1302). We need to adapt our reactions emotions or control their intensity, duration or behavioral and physiognomic expression. Cognitive reappraisal and expressive suppression are two ways of regulating emotions which is a matter of changing the way we think about or react to an emotion-provoking event (John & Gross, 2004). Given that emotions integrate “a series of evaluations enabling the individual to specify the meaning of the situation in his or her eyes” (Cuisinier & Pons, 2011, p. 3).

It is difficult for adults to manage their emotions, let alone children. However, there are techniques we can borrow from NLP that are likely to produce beneficial results for learners: “*anchoring offers the possibility of changing out internal state to experience situations of our choice in better conditions. It enables us to put ourselves in a specific state, reinforce it and channel it*” (Mouzoune, 2010, p. 60). The anchoring technique is an effective remedy for managing negative emotions. It is the process of associating an internal response (a positive emotion or calm state) with an external or internal trigger (image, jewel, body gesture, song...) in such a way this trigger can quickly bring out

this response (Dilts, 2009). By visualizing a serene, joyful situation, the learner can exchange negative emotions for new emotions of calm and joviality experienced during their visualized journey. By linking this situation to an anchor, which can be visual, auditory, kinesthetic, olfactory or gustatory (Mouzoune, 2010), they can stimulate this state, and maintain their positive emotions whenever an unpleasant emotion invades.

- **Using emotion:** acting calmly to improve emotional identity. Every time a child feels a negative emotion, they do not have a good self-image (Fanget, 2003, p. 18). It is important to be aware of your child's emotions, to help them express these, to explain that it is normal to experience them, because life is full of good and bad moments. Nevertheless; they have to move on and try to get out of this negative emotional state by gradually learning to regulate their emotions.

The accumulation of these emotional experiences has only positive consequences for the child's emotional identity.

7. Conclusion

Negative emotions are triggered by something that is unacceptable to the student or anyone else. All we have to do is act on the triggering object to tame this emotion. definitely, life is full of triggers that we unfortunately cannot control. Acquiring emotion management skills is the best solution that can be used to help students soothe the emotions that can make them feel uncomfortable in class and consequently, inhibit their learning, or make life at school difficult, even hellish.

Taking into account the role of emotions in learning is indeed difficult, but, as Philippe Meirieu points out, *“keeping emotion at a distance and not denying its importance either as an obstacle or as a vector in the pedagogical relationship”* (Guyon, 2019, p. 12), does not serve the proper development of elementary school learners being their young age. Managing emotions can also be important for children’s psychological and cognitive development.

What is certain is that teachers can help students control their emotions if they, as teachers, can. We need to set a good example, on the one hand by being calm in order to arrive at the most soothing solutions with children, and on the other, by helping them to manage their emotions and become more emotionally rested.

The status of emotions in learning needs to be addressed by Didactics and Pedagogy, so that teachers can be equipped with pedagogical and didactic methods to help them cope with learner’s emotions and how to manage them. In view of the fact that emotional management is an essential skill for teachers, it is of the utmost importance that it should be integrated into the professional training of future teachers, as they will, for the first time, be faced with a large number of students with divergent mentalities, different learning profiles and dissimilar emotional profiles. These teachers are expected to be in a serene emotional state, and know how to maintain their composure in the various situations they may encounter with a heterogeneous class.

An empirical approach is desirable, and what was proposed as a solution could provide a clear-cut answer to our reasoning.

References:

- Cuisinier, F., & Pons, F. (2011). *Emotions et cognition en classe*. HAL open science. <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-00749604>
- Dilts, R. (2009, August 29). L'ancrage en PNL. *Institut Repère*. <https://www.institut-repere.com/info/ancrage-pnl/>
- Doron, R., & Parot, F. (2007). *Dictionnaire de Psychologie* (2nd ed.). QUADRIGE/PUF.
- Fanget, F. (2003). *OSER: Thérapie de la confiance en soi*. Odile Jacob. <https://books.google.co.ma/books?id=rcPOWK7HUiwC&printsec=frontcover&hl=fr#v=onepage&q&f=false>
- Gentaz, É. (2017). Compétences émotionnelles chez l'enfant: Comment les développer ? *Les Cahiers Dynamiques*, 71(1), 24. <https://doi.org/10.3917/lcd.071.0024>
- Gläser-Zikuda, M., & Mayring, P. (2004). Développer le plaisir d'apprendre à l'école. In *Les émotions à l'école*. Presses de l'Université du Québec.
- Gueguen, C. (2018). *Heureux d'apprendre à l'école*. Les Arènes. Robert Laffont.
- Guyon, R. (2019). Entretien avec Philippe Meirieu. *Diversité*, 195. <https://cdn.reseau-canope.fr/archivage/valid/extraits/590001-29225-37637.pdf>
- Higy-Lang, C., & Gellman, C. (2000). *LE COACHING* (Éditions d'Organisation). https://www.academia.edu/9565688/Le_coaching
- Imbert, G. (2010). L'entretien semi-directif: À la frontière de la santé publique et de l'anthropologie: *Recherche en soins infirmiers*, N° 102(3), 23–34. <https://doi.org/10.3917/rsi.102.0023>
- John, O. P., & Gross, J. J. (2004). Healthy and Unhealthy Emotion Regulation: Personality Processes, Individual Differences, and Life Span Development. *Journal of Personality*, 72(6), 1301–1334. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6494.2004.00298.x>
- Karyn D. Hall. (2014, October 14). Help for the Emotionally Sensitive. *New Harbinger Publications, Inc.* <https://www.newharbinger.com/blog/self-help/help-for-the-emotionally-sensitive-a-qa-with-karyn-d-hall-phd/>
- Kitzinger, J., Marková, I., & Kalamalikis, N. (2004). Qu'est-ce que les focus groups ? *Bulletin de Psychologie*, tome 57. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/47685665_Qu'est-ce_que_les_focus_groups
- Kurz, A., Reddy, L. A., & Glover, T. A. (2017). A Multidisciplinary Framework of Instructional Coaching. *Theory Into Practice*, 56(1), 66–77. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405841.2016.1260404>

- Lafortune, L., Doudin, P.-A., Pons, F., & Hancock, D. R. (2004). *Les émotions à l'école* (Presses de l'Université du Québec).
- Malrieu, P. (1956). La vie affective de l'enfant. In *Psychologie de l'enfant, de la naissance à l'adolescence: Vol. Cahiers de Pédagogie Moderne* (13th ed.). Librairie Armand Colin.
- Mikolajczak, M. (2020). *Les compétences émotionnelles*. Dunod.
https://www.dunod.com/sites/default/files/atoms/files/Feuilletage_988.pdf
- Mouzoune, K. (2010). *Le coaching pédagogique—Comment vaincre les difficultés scolaires* (L'Harmattan).
- Napoli, J. (2022). Quelques conséquences de la pandémie de covid-19 sur la méthodologie de recherche qualitative en sciences de l'éducation: *Raisons éducatives*, N° 26(1), 305–317. <https://doi.org/10.3917/raised.026.0305>
- Pekrun, R. (2014). Emotions and Learning. *EDUCATIONAL PRACTICES SERIES—24*, 24.
<http://www.ibe.unesco.org/publications.htm>
- Pierre Angel & Patrick Amar. (2015). *Le Coaching (QUE SAIS-JE ?)*. Presses Universitaires de France.
- Retuerta, S. (2016). *Mieux vivre avec SES ÉMOTIONS. Au travail ou en privé, comment développer son leadership émotionnel*. GERESO EDITION.
- Robert, P. (2011). *LE PETIT ROBERT 2012*. Le Robert.
- Rutledge, P. (2016). *Everything is Story: Telling Stories and Positive Psychology*.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343921003_Everything_is_Story_Telling_Stories_and_Positive_Psychology
- Sillamy, N. (2010). *Dictionnaire de Psychologie* (2nd ed.). LAROUSSE.
- Sprung, M., Münch, H. M., Harris, P. L., Ebesutani, C., & Hofmann, S. G. (2015). Children's emotion understanding: A meta-analysis of training studies. *Developmental Review*, 37, 41–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dr.2015.05.001>
- Tamisier, J.-C. (1999). *Grand Dictionnaire de la Psychologie* (2nd ed.). Larousse-Bordas.

Appendix:

-Questions of the focus group:

1. Aimes-tu l'école?
2. Qu'est-ce que tu ressens quand tu prends le chemin de l'école ?
 La joie la peur la tristesse
 La colère le dégoût la panique
3. Tu préfères l'arabe ou le français ? Pourquoi ?
4. Quand tu réponds juste à une question, qu'est-ce que ton (ta) professeur(e) te dit ?
5. Comment tu te sens quand il (elle) te félicite ?
6. Et qu'est-ce que tu ressens quand ton professeur te dit que ta réponse est fausse ?
Tu es : triste, furieux, honteux, démotivé, en colère...
7. Si, par exemple, un jour ton (ta) professeur(e) te réprimande parce que tu t'es trompé ou tu as fait une bêtise, comment te sens-tu ?
8. Et si ton professeur t'encourage dans tes apprentissages, est-ce que cela t'affecte ?
Comment te sens-tu?
9. L'encouragement est-il important pour toi ?
10. Face à une difficulté ; tu n'as pas compris une chose ou un exercice difficile à résoudre, comment te sens-tu ?
11. Est-ce que tu le dis à ton (ta) professeur(e) ? Pourquoi ?
12. Quand ton (ta) professeur propose une activité hors classe, est-ce que cela te plaît (te motive) ?

-Questions for the semi-directive interview:

1. Vous travaillez dans une zone : urbaine – rurale
2. Vous êtes : titulaire – contractuel
3. Vos années d'expérience :
4. Niveau enseigné :
5. Langue enseignée :
6. Quand vous félicitez un élève, qu'est-ce qu'il ressent ? (D'après son comportement : fier, heureux...)
7. Quand vous dites à un élève que sa réponse est fausse, que ressent-il d'après-vous ? (Triste, furieux...)
8. Si vous réprimandez un apprenant pour une bêtise, dans quel état émotionnel devient-il ?

9. Quand ses camarades l'applaudissent suite à une bonne action, à votre avis que ressent-il ?
10. Vos encouragements pour vos élèves déclenchent quelle émotion chez eux ? (La joie, la panique...)
11. D'une manière générale, quelles sont les émotions les plus manifestées chez l'élève en classe ? (La joie, la peur, la panique, la tristesse, la colère, le dégoût)
12. D'une manière générale, quelles sont les émotions les plus manifestées chez l'élève pendant la récréation ? (La joie, la peur, la panique, la tristesse, la colère, le dégoût)
13. Si un élève a besoin de votre aide pour résoudre un problème par exemple, arrive-t-il à l'exprimer ? Si votre réponse est non, pourquoi d'après vous ?
14. Réagissez-vous d'une manière différente avec les élèves sensibles émotionnellement ? Si oui, quelle(s) stratégie(s) adoptez-vous avec eux ?